

TENSILE AND COMPRESSIVE STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOR

OF HEAT TREATED BORON-ALUMINUM^a

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Abstract

The influence of heat treatment on the tensile and compressive stress-strain behavior of six boron-aluminum (B/6061 Al) laminates was investigated. The laminates were $[0_0]$ and $[0_6]$, $[90_0]$, $[\pm 45]_S$, $[0/\pm 45/0]_S$, $[0/\pm 45]_S$, and $[\pm 45/0]_S$. The heat treatments were "as fabricated," T6, and T6N, where the T6N treatment was a T6 treatment followed by cryogenic quench in liquid nitrogen. Tensile and compressive stress-strain curves were obtained for monotonic loading to failure, and for four or five cycles of loading to successively higher load levels.

For all of the laminates, the tensile and compressive proportional limits were higher in the T6 temper than in the "as fabricated" condition. The T6N treatment affected the unidirectional laminate the most; the magnitude of the proportional limits for the T6N-condition specimens was 46 percent higher in tension but 52 percent lower in compression than the T6-condition specimens.

Cyclic loading extended the linear elastic range of all laminates with all temper conditions. The linear elastic range of the T6-condition specimens was larger than that of the "as fabricated" specimen after cycling to the same load. The cryogenic quench did not change the response to cyclic loading except to change the initial proportional limit. The permanent strain at the end of a cycle of loading depended on the laminate, the maximum load, and the heat treatment. The elastic modulus of laminates with $\pm 45^\circ$ plies was lower for each successive cycle of load.

^aThis work was partially supported by NASA Grant NGR 47-004-129

Introduction

Experimental investigations have shown that the stress-strain behavior of boron-aluminum laminates is nonlinear and, for some laminates, that the linear-elastic region of material behavior is only a small fraction of the failure strain (1,2). Several researchers have attempted to extend the elastic strain range by heat treating the laminate to raise the yield strength of the matrix (3-6). However, in most cases the investigations were limited to tensile loading of unidirectional boron-aluminum. In a previous paper (7), the influence of heat treatment and cyclic mechanical loading on the tensile stress-strain behavior of unidirectional and angle-ply laminates was discussed. Microstructural changes in the aluminum matrix resulting from tempering, residual stresses induced during fabrication, and prior nonlinear deformation of the matrix were found to have considerable influence on the tensile stress-strain response. Although those studies gave much insight into the nonlinear behavior of boron-aluminum, the effect of heat treatment on both the tensile and compressive behavior of unidirectional and angle-ply laminates has not been completely determined.

The present paper reports the effects of heat treatment and cyclic mechanical loading on the compressive stress-strain behavior of six boron-aluminum laminates. Some specimens were heat treated or heat treated and quenched in liquid nitrogen prior to testing; others were tested in the "as fabricated" condition. For the present study, specimens were monotonically and cyclically loaded in compression. The tension data to the same laminates were reported previously in References 7 and 8 and are included here for comparison. The same test procedures and heat treatments were used in all three investigations.

Experimental Program

Materials and Specimens

The experimental program involved six different laminate configurations: $[0_8]$ and $[0_6]$, $[90_8]$, $[\pm 45]_8$, $[0/\pm 45/0]_8$, $[0/\pm 45]_8$, $[\pm 45/0]_8$. The constituents of the boron-aluminum composite were 0.142 mm diameter boron fibers and 6061 aluminum alloy matrix. The laminates were received from the manufacturer in 300 by 500 mm panels. The specimens were cut with a diamond impregnated cutting wheel, and rough edges or burrs were filed off by hand. The fiber volume fraction, for each panel, varied between 47 and 48 percent. The strength of the boron fibers themselves was determined by the post-bending method and was found to be greater than 3720 MPa.

The compression specimen used in this investigation was like that used by Grimes et al in their investigation of resin matrix composites (9). It was 25.4 mm wide and nominally 220 mm long. Fiberglass tabs were bonded to the ends, leaving a gage section 90 mm long. The ends were ground flat and parallel so that loading was uniform. A small rosette strain gage was mounted on one side of the specimen for measuring strain at angles of 0° , 90° , and 45° to the loading direction.

During the compression tests, a side-support steel test fixture like that used in Reference 9 prevented buckling. A photograph of the compression specimen and side-support fixture is shown in Figure 1. The surfaces of the side-support fixture that rubbed the specimen were sprayed with a dry lubricant to minimize load transfer into the fixture by friction. The fixture was then bolted together applying a small torque to the bolts. The strain gage on the specimen was located under a cut-out area of the side-support

Fig. 1 - Compression specimen and steel side-support fixture.

fixture and the lead wires were connected to the gage through a hole in the fixture. Compressive loads were introduced into the specimen by bearing directly on the ends; no grips were used.

The three heat treatments were "as fabricated" (F), T6, and a modified T6 (T6N). Before heat treating, the specimens were cleaned by a standard acid cleaning process, described in Reference 8, to remove any grease or residue which might react with the aluminum or boron at elevated temperature. The cleaning also produced a stable oxide on the aluminum surface which acted as a protective coating for the aluminum alloy.

During the T6 heat treatment, the specimens were solution treated at 800 K for 30 minutes and then quenched in distilled water at room temperature. After quenching the specimens were annealed at 450 K for eight hours. The T6N heat treatment was a T6 treatment followed by quenching in liquid nitrogen, 77 K, for five minutes.

Test Procedures and Data Reduction

All tests were performed in a hydraulic testing machine and strain and load data were recorded by a general-purpose data-acquisition system. All laminates were tested in monotonic and cyclic compression. Two or three specimens of each type were tested. In the cyclic tests the specimens were cycled three or four times and then loaded to failure. The maximum loads for each successive cycle were 25, 50, and 75 percent or 20, 40, 60, and 80 percent of the failure loads measured in the monotonic tests. The

loading rate for monotonic tests and the loading and unloading rate for cyclic tests was 0.005 strain per minute.

Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio were calculated using least squares straight line fits to the stress-strain data in the linear elastic region. The proportional limit was measured from the stress-strain curves as the first point at which the stress-strain curve deviated from the initial linear response.

Strains measured on the steel side-support fixture during the monotonic tests indicated that a small portion of the applied load was initially transferred into the fixture. When the strain in the specimen reached approximately 0.0001, the specimen apparently began slipping and the load in the fixture remained constant thereafter. Using this strain data and the modulus of the steel, the load in the side-support fixture was computed and the load on the specimen was reduced accordingly. The load was never more than 10 percent of the specimen strength for data presented. All stresses for monotonic tests were calculated from loads that were corrected in this way.

Fixture loading during the cyclic tests was somewhat more complicated than during the monotonic tests. Not only was the fixture loaded at the beginning of each cycle, but it also unloaded completely during the initial 0.0001 change in strain when the specimen was unloaded from the peak load of the cycle. Thus, the loads during the loading portion of each cycle were corrected for fixture loading like those in the monotonic tests. However, the loads during unloading did not require correcting because the fixture unloaded initially. All the stresses for cyclic tests were also calculated from loads that were corrected to account for fixture loading.

Results and Discussion

Monotonic Tests

The mechanical properties from the monotonic tension and compression tests on all six laminates are presented in Tables I and II. As expected, the fiber-dominated laminates had higher Young's moduli than did the matrix-dominated laminates. However, the moduli of the $[0/\pm 45/0]_S$, $[0/\pm 45]_S$, $[\pm 45/0]_S$, $[\pm 45]_S$, and $[90]_S$ were not dramatically different. The moduli of those five laminates were between 131 GPa and 166 GPa, indicating that the off-axis fibers contribute significantly to Young's modulus. For each laminate, the tensile and compressive moduli were essentially the same. Other published results have shown that the tensile and compressive moduli are equal for boron-aluminum and others have shown that they are different (2, 10, 11). Results from tests of sandwich beams tend to be higher than those of axially loaded specimens.

The proportional limit for all T6 laminates was much higher than that for the same laminate in the F condition because the proportional limit of the aluminum matrix was much higher for the T6 heat treatment. In general, the compressive proportional limits of the laminates were higher than the tensile proportional limits for the same heat treatment. The higher compression values are due to residual thermal stresses in the loading direction, which are tension in the matrix and compression in the fibers. Because the matrix has a greater coefficient of thermal expansion than the fiber, these stresses develop while cooling from the high temperatures that are applied during diffusion bonding or heat treating. For the unidirectional laminates the tensile residual stresses in the aluminum matrix, as determined by x-ray diffraction, were 90 MPa for the F-condition specimens, 160 MPa for the T6,

Table I. Tensile Monotonic Stress-Strain Properties^a

Laminate	Heat Treatment	Young's Modulus, GPa	Poisson's Ratio	Proportional Limit, MPa	Failure Strength, MPa	Failure Strain
[0 ₈]	F	213	0.218	215	1770	0.00924
		225	0.181	210	1680	0.00835
		246	0.165	174	1790	0.00898
		b228	0.188	200	1750	0.00886
	T6	244	0.213	507	1330	0.00622
		230	0.236	499	1270	0.00604
		224	0.220	657	1240	0.00613
		234	0.223	554	1280	0.00613
	T6N	229	0.191	841	1230	0.00563
		228	0.229	827	1250	0.00580
		230	0.220	752	1160	0.00525
		229	0.213	807	1210	0.00556
[90 ₈]	F	143	0.164	58.8	159	0.00921
		148	0.085	51.6	135	0.00464
		132	0.058	36.5	163	0.0108
		141	0.102	49.0	152	0.00822
	T6	144	0.122	175	311	0.00291
		150	0.141	197	325	0.00258
		148	0.111	177	319	0.00309
		147	0.125	183	318	0.00286
	T6N	139	0.110	175	316	0.00286
		134	0.121	194	317	0.00310
		139	0.111	166	313	0.00303
		137	0.114	187	315	0.00300
[±45] _S	F	156	0.284	24.6	304	^c >0.03
		128	0.373	44.5	410	^c >0.03
		146	0.438	50.5	359	^c >0.03
		144	0.365	39.9	358	>0.03
	T6	147	0.343	108	370	0.0246
		146	0.281	141	396	0.0299
		147	0.312	124	383	0.0273
	T6N	131	0.319	105	324	0.0122
		152	0.344	127	325	0.00680
		142	0.332	116	325	0.00950

^aData from References 7 and 8.

^bAverage value for heat treatment.

^cStrain gage adhesive failed at approximately this strain.

Table I. Tensile Monotonic Stress-Strain Properties-Concluded

Laminate	Heat Treatment	Young's Modulus, GPa	Poisson's Ratio	Proportional Limit, MPa	Failure Strength, MPa	Failure Strain
[0/±45/0] _S	F	170	0.282	73.8	683	0.00605
		168	0.271	65.6	660	0.00602
		165	0.269	73.8	710	0.00656
		168	0.274	71.1	684	0.00621
	T6	163	0.267	170	696	0.00569
		165	0.296	159	703	0.00557
		164	0.282	165	700	0.00563
	T6N	163	0.249	159	752	0.00581
		166	0.277	179	752	0.00576
		165	0.263	169	752	0.00579
[0/±45] _S	F	159	0.295	58.1	476	0.00558
		153	0.301	50.5	528	0.00633
		163	0.268	69.0	501	0.00608
		158	0.288	59.2	502	0.00600
	T6	127	0.282	99.3	601	0.00634
		143	0.311	91.7	606	0.00624
		135	0.297	95.5	604	0.00629
	T6N	139	0.285	129	618	0.00618
		147	0.308	120	630	0.00621
		143	0.297	125	624	0.00620
[±45/0] _S	F	148	0.325	64.1	503	0.00625
		166	0.139	56.3	532	0.00648
		176	0.117	59.8	492	0.00571
		163	0.194	60.1	509	0.00615
	T6	148	0.248	143	659	0.00706
		150	0.338	155	703	0.00729
		149	0.293	149	681	0.00718
	T6N	148	0.329	155	643	0.00638
		157	0.283	89.6	600	0.00582
		153	0.306	122	622	0.00610

Table II. Compressive Monotonic Stress-Strain Properties

Laminate	Heat Treatment	Young's Modulus, GPa	Poisson's Ratio	Proportional Limit, MPa	
[0 ₆]	F	208	0.320	476	
		226	0.243	450	
		^a 217	0.332	463	
	T6	240	0.206	1170	
		233	0.197	941	
		237	0.202	1060	
	T6N	217	0.184	372	
		219	0.209	593	
		218	0.197	482	
[90 ₈]	F	141	b ₋	c ₋	
		143	b ₋	c ₋	
		161	b ₋	c ₋	
		148	-	-	
	T6	136	0.127	131	
		134	0.139	123	
		135	0.133	127	
	T6N	143	0.140	174	
		144	0.135	188	
		144	0.135	181	
	[±45] _S	F	129	0.364	53.8
			126	0.456	55.2
121			0.412	54.5	
125			0.411	54.5	
T6		131	0.361	198	
		161	0.345	221	
		146	0.353	210	
T6N		149	0.322	160	
		119	0.376	196	
		134	0.349	178	

^aAverage value for heat treatment.

^bThe transverse strains were too small to measure.

^cThere was no linear region.

Table II. Compressive Monotonic Stress-Strain Properties-Concluded

Laminate	Heat Treatment	Young's Modulus, GPa	Poisson's Ratio	Proportional Limit, MPa
[0/±45/0] _S	F	148	0.400	103
		160	0.322	83
		154	0.361	93
	T6	167	0.304	552
		165	0.285	294
		166	0.295	423
	T6N	169	0.280	325
		158	0.305	264
		164	0.293	296
[0/±45] _S	F	119	0.480	105
		138	0.384	60.7
		129	0.432	82.8
	T6	151	0.337	205
		158	0.320	266
		155	0.329	236
	T6N	137	0.339	223
		145	0.345	243
		141	0.342	233
[±45/0] _S	F	133	0.455	74.5
		149	0.331	112
		141	0.393	93.3
	T6	137	0.303	191
		148	0.311	236
		143	0.307	214
	T6N	163	0.412	221
		150	0.309	239
		157	0.361	230

and 83 MPa for the T6N specimens. This reduction of the residual stress in the T6N specimens produced a proportional limit 46 percent higher in tension and 52 percent lower in compression than that in the T6 condition. The effect of the T6N treatment on the proportional limit of other laminates was less pronounced.

The tensile strengths of all the laminates in the T6 and T6N conditions (except the $[0_8]$ laminates) were higher than those in the F condition due to the higher strength of the matrix. The strengths of the T6 and T6N $[0_8]$ laminates were not higher than the F-condition laminate because the heat treatment also reduced the strength of the fibers. Thus the effect of the reduction in fiber strength was greater than that of the strengthened T6 condition matrix. Groups of fibers leached from the F- and T6-condition specimens were tested using a post bending procedure. The strength of the fibers from the heat treated material was found to be 10 percent lower than the strength of the fibers from the F-condition material. The difference between strengths of T6- and T6N-condition laminates is not consistent and is not large.

Compressive ultimate strengths are not reported because the failures typically occurred outside of the gage section. The failure was usually associated with debonding of the fiberglass tab and subsequent buckling of the laminate or brooming of the end of the specimen. Because of these problems this type of specimen is not suitable for measuring the ultimate compressive strength of metal matrix composite laminates.

Examples of tension and compression stress-strain curves for $[0_8]$ or $[0_6]$, $[\pm 45]_S$, and $[0/\pm 45]_S$ laminates with all three heat treatments are shown in Figure 2. The curves for the $[0_6]$ or $[0_8]$ laminates are nearly linear to failure whereas the $[\pm 45]_S$ curves are very nonlinear and have relatively high strains to failure. The $[0/\pm 45]_S$ curves are somewhat nonlinear due to the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, but the strain at failure in tension was limited by the 0° plies. The curves for the other laminates with both $\pm 45^\circ$ and 0° plies are similar to those of the $[0/\pm 45]_S$ laminate.

Cyclic Tests

Specimens were tested in cyclic tension and cyclic compression to further characterize the nonlinear stress-strain response of the boron-aluminum laminates. Of particular significance was the effect of heat treatment on the yield behavior and permanent set. The cryogenic quench affected only the initial proportional limit; after the load exceeded the initial proportional limit, the stress-strain curves for subsequent cycles were the same for the T6- and T6N-condition specimens of a given laminate. Hence, cyclic tests results for only F- and T6-condition laminates are presented for all laminates except for the $[0_8]$ cyclic tension specimen, which was tested only in the F and T6N condition.

The $[0/\pm 45]$ Family of Laminates - Figure 3 shows the effect of heat treatment on the cyclic tensile stress-strain response of the $[0/\pm 45]_S$ laminate. Both the F- and T6-condition specimens strain hardened when cyclically loaded and the linear elastic ranges increased with subsequent cycles to a maximum range (tick marks indicate the linear elastic range for loading and unloading in the figures). Table III shows the linear elastic

Fig. 2 - Tensile and compressive stress-strain curves of $[0_8]$ or $[0_6]$, $[0/\pm 45]_S$, and $[\pm 45]_S$ boron-aluminum with three different heat treatments.

Fig. 3 - Cyclic tension stress-strain curves for $[0/\pm 45]_S$ boron-aluminum.

Table IIIa. Linear Elastic Range of $[0/\pm 45]_S$ Boron-Aluminum during Cyclic Tensile Loading

Cycle	Linear Elastic Range, MPa			
	F Condition		T6 Condition	
	Loading	Unloading	Loading	Unloading
I	62	Linear	Linear	Linear
II	131	179	145	Linear
III	152	165	269	Linear
IV	152	---	262	326
V	---	---	207	---

Table IIIb. Linear Elastic Range of $[0/\pm 45]_S$ Boron-Aluminum during Cyclic Compressive Loading

Cycle	Linear Elastic Range, MPa			
	F Condition		T6 Condition	
	Loading	Unloading	Loading	Unloading
I	62	179	234	Linear
II	248	228	241	352
III	179	186	407	331
IV	186	200	414	331
V	193	---	345	---

^aData from Reference 8

ranges for loading and unloading for each cycle. The maximum linear elastic range of the T6-condition specimen was always larger than that of the F-condition specimen. The specimens unloaded linearly during the first two or three cycles but unloaded nonlinearly thereafter. The permanent strain of the F-condition specimen was greater than that of the T6 specimen for the first two cycles, but less than the permanent strain of the T6-condition specimen thereafter.

The $[0/\pm 45/0]_S$, $[\pm 45/0]_S$ and $[0/\pm 45]_S$ laminates exhibited modulus reduction on each cycle of loading (see Table IV). The reduction in modulus was probably caused by some kind of damage to the fibers and matrix.

Figure 4 shows compressive stress-strain curves for F- and T6-condition $[0/\pm 45]_S$ laminates. As in tension, both types of specimens strain hardened and the linear-elastic ranges increased with subsequent cycles to a maximum range (Table IV). The maximum linear-elastic range of the F-condition specimen was less than that of the T6-condition specimen. Except for the first cycle of load on the T6 specimen, unloading was nonlinear for both heat treatments. For the first two cycles of loading the permanent strain was greater for the F-condition specimen, but at the end of the third and fourth cycles the permanent strain was greatest for the T6-condition specimen.

The linear unloading during the initial cycles and the nonlinear unloading on subsequent cycles can be explained by considering the stress-strain histories of the fiber and matrix during two consecutive cycles of loading as shown in Figure 5. In order to simplify the discussion, the fiber is assumed to behave in a linear elastic manner, the matrix to be elastic-perfectly plastic, and the fiber and matrix to be without residual stresses initially. These simplifications do not change the basic reason for linear and nonlinear unloading. When the composite is loaded to the strain ϵ_1 in cycle one, the matrix, and thus the composite, yields at the strain ϵ_m . When the composite is unloaded, the matrix and fiber unload linearly to points a and a' respectively where they are in equilibrium. When the

Fig. 4 - Cyclic compression stress-strain curves for $[0/\pm 45]_S$ boron-aluminum.

Fig. 5 - Stress-strain curves of fiber and matrix during cyclic loading.

Table IV. Elastic Modulus for Cyclic Tension Loading and Unloading of Boron-Aluminum Laminates^a

Heat Treatment	Cycle	Laminate Configuration							
		[±45] _s		[0/±45/0] _s		[0/±45] _s		[±45/0] _s	
		E _x ^L (GPa)	E _x ^{UL} (GPa)						
F	I	141	163	178	173	156	132	166	156
	II	155	142	170	161	144	137	154	145
	III	138	129	166	154	136	128	152	138
	IV	131	--	161	--	131	--	148	--
T6	I	142	148	163	170	144	156	164	169
	II	138	141	170	164	154	151	163	159
	III	139	141	166	161	148	141	159	154
	IV	138	137	162	--	141	135	156	149
	V	134	130	--	--	142	--	152	--
	VI	131	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
T6N	I	145	150	163	170	142	156	153	152
	II	143	149	165	167	144	141	154	150
	III	145	135	163	159	139	133	152	149
	IV	134	124	159	--	134	130	150	148
	V	124	116	--	--	134	--	149	--
	VI	117	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

^aData from Reference 8.

E_x^L Denotes Elastic Modulus for the Loading Portion of the Cycle.

E_x^{UL} Denotes Elastic Modulus for the Unloading Portion of the Cycle.

composite is reloaded to the higher strain ϵ_2 in cycle two, the fiber responds elastically and the matrix yields again. Now when the composite is unloaded from the higher strain ϵ_2 , the fiber unloads to point b' and the matrix yields in compression and plastically deforms to point b where the fiber and matrix are in equilibrium. From Figure 5b, the matrix will always yield in compression when the recovered strain on unloading ($\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_b$) exceeds $2\epsilon_m$, the total elastic strain range of the matrix.

The [0_g] and [0₆] Laminates - Figure 6 shows the cyclic tension stress-strain curves for [0_g] boron-aluminum with F and T6N heat treatments. The F-condition specimen yielded on the first cycle. During the first two cycles the specimen strain hardened due to plastic deformation and the linear elastic range increased. However, for the remaining cycles the linear elastic range was constant during loading and unloading. The T6N specimen, however, did not strain harden on the first three cycles because the applied stress was less than the proportional limit of the laminate; the proportional limit was exceeded only during the final cycle.

Cyclic compression stress-strain curves for the [0] laminate with F and T6 heat treatments are shown in Figure 7. The compressive strain hardening behavior of the F-condition specimen was much like that in tension. The

Fig. 6 - Cyclic tension stress-strain curves for $[0_8]$ boron-aluminum.

Fig. 7 - Cyclic compression stress-strain curves for $[0_6]$ boron-aluminum.

maximum linear elastic range in compression was greater than that in tension. Contrary to the F-condition specimen, the T6-condition specimen did not show a constant linear-elastic range; rather, the specimen strain hardened when plastically deformed, and on subsequent cycles the proportional limit was approximately equal to the highest previous stress. Unloading was always linear with a slope equal to the initial elastic modulus. No significant permanent strain was developed in either the T6 or F condition specimen.

The $[\pm 45]_S$ Laminate - Figure 8 shows cyclic tension stress-strain curves for F- and T6-condition $[\pm 45]_S$ boron-aluminum specimens. The stress-strain response of this laminate was very nonlinear because the fibers are loaded through the matrix and the matrix is stressed beyond its yield point. The cyclic behavior was similar to that of a ductile metal in that whenever the proportional limit was exceeded during a cycle of loading the proportional limit increased on the subsequent cycle to the maximum stress of the previous cycle and unloading was always linear. This laminate responded linearly

Fig. 8 - Cyclic tension stress-strain curves for $[\pm 45]_S$ boron-aluminum.

during unloading because the total elastic strain range of the aluminum ($2\epsilon_m$, Fig. 5) was not exceeded during the unloading portion of the cycle. The total linear elastic strain was not exceeded because no 0° fibers were present to force the matrix into compression on unloading. The permanent strains were lower for the T6-condition than the F-condition after both specimens were loaded to the same stress.

Results in Table IV for the cyclic tension tests show the elastic modulus for $[\pm 45]_S$ decreased in each succeeding cycle. This reduction in modulus was probably the result of damage in the specimen.

No compression data are presented for the $[\pm 45]_S$ laminate because the load in the fixture was a significant proportion of the total applied load, and the stress in the specimen could not be calculated accurately.

Conclusion

The tensile and compressive stress-strain behavior of boron-aluminum composites having several laminate orientations and several heat treatments was studied. Heat treating to a T6 and T6N (T6 with liquid nitrogen quench) condition produced a greater linear elastic range for both tensile and compressive loading than was observed in the "as fabricated" specimens. Only the proportional limit of the unidirectional laminate was significantly different for the T6 and T6N conditions. The elastic modulus for tensile and compressive loading was the same for all heat treatments.

Cyclic tests were performed to characterize the strain hardening behavior of the laminates. The linear elastic range of the T6- and T6N-

condition specimens was larger than that of the F-condition specimen. Cyclic loading in tension or compression strain hardened the specimen and extended the linear elastic range. Specimens in T6 and T6N condition strain hardened more than did F-condition specimens. For laminates containing 0° plies, the stress-strain behavior on unloading was nonlinear, whereas other laminates always unloaded linearly. All of the laminates containing ±45° plies exhibited a modulus reduction when cyclically loaded in tension.

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